

Coupled Diffusion of Aqueous Electrolytes across Bentonite Clay Membrane

SAROJ KUMAR SANYAL* and SUJATA DE

Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Mohanpur-741 252

Manuscript received 23 December 1992

In soil, coupling between various transport processes occurring simultaneously often leads to a flow of one kind from a non-conjugate force. Such coupled movement of salt and water in soils and clays is of interest from theoretical viewpoint and also from practical considerations. The present study reports coupled isothermal diffusion encountered in dilute aqueous solutions of HCl, H₂SO₄, NaCl, Na₂SO₄, KCl, K₂SO₄, MgCl₂, MgSO₄ and CaCl₂ across a bentonite clay membrane, in hydrogen and calcium forms, at 35 and 40°.

For the purpose, a specially designed osmotic cell (made of Perspex) was used in which the clay membrane was sandwiched between two solution chambers. The transport data were fitted to the formulations based on irreversible thermodynamics to obtain the reflection coefficient (σ) for the given membrane-transport systems. The latter provides a measure of the extent of 'demixing' of solute and solvent in the membrane phase, and is thus expected to lead to information on solute-solvent interactions in the membrane.

For diffusion of aqueous acids across H-bentonite, the σ values were small, indicating near complete coupling between the solute and the solvent flows. This might be attributed to the absence of any exchange reaction in the membrane phase during the passage of the acids. The isothermal transports of other aqueous solutions across H-bentonite were associated with large σ values, obviously due to an exchange reaction in the clay phase. However, among the chlorides studied, the σ values were the highest for diffusion of CaCl₂ across Ca-bentonite membrane. This is attributed to the difficulty of Na⁺ and K⁺ ions to replace Ca²⁺ from the bentonite phase, the latter having a higher bonding energy. Such a trend may also be explained in terms of a superimposed mobility effect of the hydrated cations, and also the ion-pair formation effect in the clay.

In a multicomponent systems such as soil, coupling between various transport processes occurring simultaneously often leads to a flow of one kind from a non-conjugate force. Such coupled processes are of interest, not only from theoretical viewpoint, but from practical considerations as well, especially so for irrigated arid and semi-arid soils of high salt contents¹. In an earlier publication¹, significance of such coupled transport processes while studying intricate soil-water-plant relationships, was highlighted. The usefulness of the non-equilibrium thermodynamic approach in dealing with these coupled processes was also demonstrated. Since the work of Taylor and Cary² on application of irreversible thermodynamics in coupled transport processes in soil system, there have been reports of investigations of such systems under isothermal conditions³. While summarising these studies^{2,3}, an overwhelming em-

phasis on the quantitative aspects does not escape one's attention, leaving much to be desired insofar as qualitative information, that may emerge from such investigations, is concerned. More recently, Sanyal and his associates⁴ have closely examined the phenomena of thermal/isothermal diffusion and thermo-osmosis in soil/clay systems, and pointed out the qualitative significance of several transport parameters in characterising the soil-moisture interactions.

The present work proposes to examine the coupled diffusion encountered in some aqueous electrolytes across a bentonite membrane in the H⁺ and Ca²⁺ forms at two temperatures, namely, 35 and 40°. The irreversible thermodynamic parameter, the reflection coefficient^{5,6} (σ), has been obtained by fitting the experimental data to formulations based

on irreversible thermodynamics. The reflection coefficient provides a measure of the extent of 'demixing' of solute and solvent in course of passage through the membrane, and is thus expected to provide information with regard to the interactions of solute and solvent in the membrane phase.

Theoretical relations : The dissipation function (ϕ) for transport across a clay membrane separating two aqueous solutions having different concentrations that permit an osmotic flow with a concomitant build-up of hydrostatic pressure difference may be expressed as⁶

$$\phi = J_v \Delta P + J_D \Delta \Pi \quad (1)$$

where the difference, Δ , refers to those across membrane, while J_v and J_D denote the volume and diffusion fluxes across the membrane, respectively.

By following a number of transformations^{1,6}, equation (2) is obtained leading to σ ,

$$\sigma = \left(\frac{J_D}{J_v} \right)_{\Delta\pi=0} = \left(\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta\pi} \right)_{J_v=0} = 1 - \left(\frac{V_s}{V_w} \right)_{\Delta\pi=0} \quad (2)$$

where $J_v = 0$ denotes the incidence of the steady state, and V_s and V_w are the respective velocities of solute and water relative to the membrane. For an ideally semipermeable membrane, $V_s = 0$ and $\sigma = 1$ (equation 2), whereas for an 'open' membrane ($V_s = V_w$), $\sigma = 0$. For intermediate membrane-transport systems, $0 < \sigma < 1$.

In the present study, the σ values have been reported for transport at 35 and 40° of aqueous solutions of H₂SO₄, Na₂SO₄, K₂SO₄, MgSO₄ across H-bentonite and Ca-bentonite membrane. In addition, transport of HCl, NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂ and CaCl₂ solutions has been studied across Ca-bentonite membrane.

Results and Discussion

Tables 1 and 2 record the results on reflection coefficient (σ) for transport of aqueous HCl, H₂SO₄, KCl, K₂SO₄, NaCl, Na₂SO₄, MgCl₂, MgSO₄ and CaCl₂ solutions across H- and Ca-bentonite clay membranes at 35 and 40°. Table 1 reproduces some data for HCl, KCl, NaCl, MgCl₂ and CaCl₂

solutions across H-bentonite membrane already reported earlier¹ (indicated as a foot note to Table 1) for the purpose of giving a more complete discussion of the present findings, and also for comparison of the results obtained with the two membranes studied.

TABLE 1 - REFLECTION COEFFICIENT (σ) FOR TRANSPORT OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS ACROSS HYDROGEN BENTONITE CLAY MEMBRANE

Solution	Mean Temp K	10 ⁴ σ
0.1 M HCl ^a	308	2.73
	313	2.42
H ₂ SO ₄	308	3.56
	313	3.15
NaCl ^a	308	4.04
	313	4.57
Na ₂ SO ₄	308	5.07
	313	8.67
KCl ^a	308	5.04
	313	5.71
K ₂ SO ₄	308	5.66
	313	9.44
MgCl ₂ ^a	308	4.32
	313	4.96
MgSO ₄	308	8.98
	313	12.2
CaCl ₂ ^a	308	4.39
	313	5.07

^aDate taken from Ref. 1.

For diffusion of the aqueous acid across H-bentonite, the σ values are found to be rather small (Table 1). Because the passage of H⁺ ion across H-bentonite membrane should not involve any exchange, there does not seem to be any lag between the solute and solvent flows, i.e. there is a nearly complete coupling between the total volume flux of solvent and solute transmission, and hence σ approaches zero. However, among the aqueous chlorides studied, the σ values were found to be the highest for diffusion of CaCl₂ across Ca-bentonite at both the temperatures (Table 2). This may possibly be attributed to the difficulty of Na⁺ and K⁺ to replace Ca²⁺ from the bentonite phase, the latter having a higher bonding energy. It is satisfying to note in this context that the σ values for CaCl₂ and MgCl₂ were similar, in

view of similar bonding energies of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions on a given clay matrix. Such a trend may also be explained in terms of the superimposed mobility effect in that the highly hydrated Ca^{2+} in CaCl_2 , as compared to Na^+ and K^+ , is slower in motion, and also the ion-pair formation effects is more prominent in CaCl_2 than that in NaCl and KCl . These two effects would also increase the lag between the solute and the solvent flows.

TABLE 2- REFLECTION COEFFICIENT (σ) FOR TRANSPORT OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS ACROSS CALCIUM BENTONITE CLAY MEMBRANE

Solution	Mean Temp K	$10^4 \sigma$
0.1 M HCl	308	9.55
	313	13.2
H ₂ SO ₄	308	10.6
	313	15.8
NaCl	308	6.75
	313	10.6
Na ₂ SO ₄	308	8.07
	313	11.0
KCl	308	6.04
	313	8.20
K ₂ SO ₄	308	7.22
	313	10.5
MgCl ₂	308	8.64
	313	13.0
MgSO ₄	308	9.60
	313	15.2
CaCl ₂	308	8.71
	313	14.2

The isothermal transports of aqueous KCl , K_2SO_4 , NaCl , Na_2SO_4 , CaCl_2 , MgCl_2 and MgSO_4 across H-bentonite membrane were associated with larger values of σ (Table 1) as compared to those for transport of aqueous HCl and H_2SO_4 , obviously because of an exchange reaction being involved in the clay phase in the former cases.

The sulphates were found to exhibit higher σ values than the corresponding chlorides (Tables 1 and 2). The lower dissociation constant of the sulphates (ion-pairs) as compared to those for the respective chlorides may be the possible cause of specific retention of these sulphates in the bentonite membrane, leading to higher σ values.

The relative exchangeability of a given cation

(hydrated) depends on its bonding energy (on the exchanger), which in turn is a function of ionic potential. It also depends on ion-pair formation energy and hydration number. A high C.E.C. of bentonite encourages further the degree of exchange process. This could mean a direct correlation between the exchanging power of a cation on the given clay surface and the corresponding σ value. Indeed, this was observed in the present study with the σ values for the chlorides or the sulphates exhibiting the following order : $\sigma_{\text{Ca}} > \sigma_{\text{Mg}} > \sigma_{\text{Na}}$. The above order of the σ values agrees with the earlier observations on relative replacing power of cations from clay and humic fraction⁸. However, K^+ being the least hydrated species among the cations studied behaves somewhat differently in exhibiting a rather high σ value for H-bentonite (higher than those for even the divalent cations). This could possibly be attributed to the specific retention of K^+ ions in the bentonite membrane. However, more remains to be done before this apparently surprising observation can be explained with a greater degree of confidence¹.

The σ values for transport of aqueous chlorides and sulphates of Ca, Mg, Na and K increased with rise in temperature for each form of bentonite. At a higher temperature, the degree of hydration of these cations is expected to be reduced to some extent due to increased thermal motion of water molecules, thus causing an increase in their bonding energy and so also the corresponding σ values. The reverse trend is found with diffusion of H^+ ion across H-bentonite. This seems to arise from a more complete coupling between the solvent and solute fluxes at an elevated temperature and the unusual transport mechanism of H^+ ions through aqueous medium. This may also be correlated with a faster movement of H^+ ions through H-bentonite at a higher temperature because of a corresponding lower degree of ionic hydration. Indeed on studying the transport of aqueous CaCl_2 across Ca-bentonite and aqueous KCl across K-bentonite⁹, both of which do not involve ionic exchange in the membrane phase, the corresponding σ values were found to register sharp decrease on increasing the electrolyte concentration. This may well have resulted from

the transport of bulkier Ca^{2+} and K^+ ions in more dilute solutions so that the lag between the solute and solvent flow becomes wider in dilute solutions.

Experimental

Isothermal diffusion cell : The design of the cell for diffusion studies across clay membranes was developed earlier by Majumdar and Sanyal¹⁰. The cell was in two parts and assembled vertically

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the osmotic cell : G = glass capillary, M = membrane, P = perspex cell S = screw, T = stopper, R = Myler sheet and W = wooden plate.

(Fig. 1). Each solution chamber (or half-cell) was cut in a perspex block in a circular fashion (4.0 cm dia \times 1.2 cm). The bottom of each half-cell was closed by an octagonal perspex sheet. The membrane was fixed with 'Araldite' gum in a circular hole (0.3 cm dia) cut in the upper wall of the lower half-cell, which completed the channel of contact between the solutions in the two half-cells via the membrane. Each half-cell was provided with a glass-capillary tube in order to facilitate the determination of the hydrostatic pressure difference across the membrane. The flat surfaces of the two half-cells in contact (excluding the membrane area) were separated from each other by means of a fine sheet of plastic for prevention of leakage, when the cell was in operation. The two half-cells were joined together by means of two small nuts screwed through the octagonal perspex sheets referred to above. The entire cell with its two parts, was pressed against two wooden plates, and the whole

set-up was held together by a number of brass nuts and bolts screwed through the outer peripheral parts of the wooden plates in order that air-tight condition was ensured. After filling up the lower half-cell with the desired aqueous solution and the upper half with water, the osmotic cell was placed inside an air-thermostat maintained at the experimental temperature.

Air-thermostat : The air-thermostat used was a wooden box (90 \times 60 \times 60 cm³). It was provided with an electric bulb (100 W) and an electric fan (REMI), as well as an electrical contact thermometer inserted through a hole into the thermostat. A relay circuit which can be operated from outside was used to maintain the inside temperature constant within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The box was insulated from the surroundings with polystyrene foam mounted on the inside of the front door. The make-and-break of the relay circuit maintained a constant temperature inside the air-thermostat over a long period of time by automatic regulation.

Preparation of clay membrane : The refined bentonite clay (organic matter-free) was treated with dilute HCl for coagulation and washed several times to make it free from nearly all the chloride. One part of the dialysed H-clay was next converted to Ca-forms by treatment with the required amount of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and finally left for 10 days with occasional stirring (the pH of the suspension should be 7.5–8.5). This was followed by dialysis for purification of the Ca-clay. The clay suspension (both the H^+ and Ca^{2+} forms) was then boiled for about 5 min and slowly poured on to a shallow copper dish previously rubbed with linen, which was soaked into liquid paraffin, and the suspension was evaporated carefully at 70–80°. The thickness of the membrane varied from 0.20 to 0.26 mm. The membrane thus prepared was cut into suitable sizes of diameter greater than 8 mm and fired at 500° for 5h in a muffle furnace. The heat-treated membranes were then mounted into the circular groove of the membrane assembly, using 'Araldite' as the adhesive, and once mounted, the membranes were found to be fairly stable for osmotic measurements.

Experimental run : The isothermal cell described above was mounted in the horizontal position with the membrane sandwiched between the two solution chambers. The lower half-cell was filled with the desired solution while the upper half with water, taking due care to exclude any entrapped air bubble. The hydrostatic pressure difference between the two chambers across the membrane and its variations were recorded by noting the solution levels in the capillary tubes with the aid of a cathetometer. The attainment of the steady state was indicated by these solution levels reaching constant values independent of time. It usually took 3–4 h time for such attainment of the steady state. This time period agreed with the requirement of the relaxation period of the given diffusion process¹¹. The cell was then dismantled and the concentration of the solutions in the two half-cells were checked by direct determinations carried out on suitable aliquots by the appropriate analytical methods (for instance, sodium and potassium concentrations were determined by using Na and K electrodes; calcium and magnesium concentrations were ascertained by means of complexometric titration using EDTA, while neutralisation titrations were resorted to for finding out H⁺ ion concentration).

The osmotic pressure difference ($\Delta\pi$) as well as the hydrostatic pressure difference (ΔP) were then estimated from these measurements and σ , the reflection coefficient, was evaluated by using these data in equation (2).

References

1. S. DE and S. K. SANYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 331.
2. S. A. TAYLOR and J. W. CARY, *Trans. Int. Congr. Soil Sci.*, 1960, **1**, 80.
3. W. D. KEMPER and J. B. ROLLINS, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1966, **30**, 529; J. LETEY and W. D. KEMPER, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1969, **33**, 25; J. LETEY, W. D. KEMPER and L. NOONAN, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1969, **33**, 15; H. W. OLSEN, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1969, **33**, 328; R. P. TRIPATHI and B. P. GHILDYAL, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1978, **26**, 313.
4. S. K. SANYAL and M. ADHIKARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1071.; *Trans. Int. Congr. Soil Sci. Abstr.*, 1982, **6**, 8; *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1984, **32**, 9; A. BHATTACHARJYA and S. K. SANYAL, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1987, **35**, 177; S. K. SANYAL and S. BANDYOPADHYAY, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1987, **35**, 487; A. K. MUKHERJEE and S. K. SANYAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 761; *Can. J. Chem.*, 1989, **67**, 867; R. KAR and S. K. SANYAL, *Clay Res.*, 1988, **7**, 1; S. K. SANYAL and R. KAR *J. Surface. Sci. Technol.*, 1990, **6**, 187; K. MAJUMDAR and S. K. SANYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 147; M. ADHIKARI, S. K. SANYAL and S. ROY CHOWDHURY, *Proc. Indian Natl. Sci. Acad., Sect. A*, 1989, **55**, 557.
5. A. J. STAVERMAN, *Recl. Trav. Chim.*, 1951, **70**, 344.
6. A. KATCHALSKY and P. F. CURRAN, "Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics in Biophysics", Harvard University Press, 1965.
7. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths, New York, 1959.
8. R. C. SRIVASTAVA and R. PAL, "Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics in Soil Physics", Oxford and IBII, New Delhi, 1973.
9. P. ROYCHOWDHURI, S. MANDAL and S. K. SANYAL, communicated.
10. K. MAJUMDAR and S. K. SANYAL, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1989, **37**, 645.
11. A. K. MUKHERJEE and S. K. SANYAL, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1986, **64**, 717.

